

Securing Europe's R&I Horizon: Call for a Researcher-Centred Framework Programme

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MARIE CURIE ALUMNI ASSOCIATION

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About the Marie Curie Alumni Association

The Marie Curie Alumni Association (MCAA) is a global network with 23,000+ members from over 150 countries, open to any past or present beneficiaries of the Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions (MSCA), not restricted to researchers, but including their supervisors and MSCA project managers. The MCAA aims to connect the MSCA community, supporting career development initiatives for MCAA members and advocating for research and researchers.

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Executive summary

The MCAA welcomes the European Commission's ambition to shape a bold and forward-looking 10th EU Framework Programme for Research and Innovation (FP10) within the next Multiannual Financial Framework (MFF).

The MCAA strongly supports the continued focus on excellent science, the standalone nature of FP10, and the increased budgetary envelope of €175 billion. It welcomes the sustained support for the European Research Council (ERC) and the MSCA, as well as the growing attention to researcher careers, inclusion, and simplification.

However, several concerns must be addressed to ensure FP10's long-term success. The integration of FP10 within the European Competitiveness Fund (ECF) and the introduction of the Competitiveness Coordination Tool (CCT) risk undermining scientific independence and bottom-up excellence. The proposed directionality of the MSCA and its potential alignment with "moonshot" projects could dilute its core mission and limit its global appeal. The ERC's scientific autonomy must be safeguarded in light of changes to its governance, and geopolitical filters in international cooperation raise concerns about openness. Moreover, the proposed FP10 budget, though higher than Horizon Europe, remains below expert recommendations and is insufficient to meet growing demand, especially in light of inflation and the expansion of Europe's research workforce.

To ensure FP10 is fit for purpose and delivers on its ambition, the MCAA puts forward five key recommendations:

- **Safeguard FP10's autonomy and excellence**

Maintain a distinct legal and governance structure for FP10, preserve bottom-up funding mechanisms, and ensure the ERC and MSCA operate with long-term independence and stability.

- **Ensure sufficient investment in the MSCA programme**

Allocate at least €25 billion to the MSCA to meet growing demand, account for inflation, and support a larger, more diverse, and increasingly specialised research workforce.

- **Strengthen researcher careers and mobility**

Fully implement the European Charter for Researchers, address precarity, and improve conditions for mobile researchers. The MSCA must remain open, bottom-up, and dedicated to training and career development.

- **Foster an inclusive European Research Area (ERA)**

Reinforce widening actions and support transition countries to close research and innovation (R&I) gaps, retain talent, and ensure broad participation in European research.

- **Promote openness and responsible international cooperation**

Advance global and open scientific collaboration, while applying research security measures in a balanced and proportionate way to safeguard critical technologies and intellectual property. This requires sustained investment in open research infrastructures and support for equitable publishing models like diamond open access.

The MCAA calls for continued dialogue and collaboration among EU institutions, Member States, and stakeholders to refine and strengthen FP10. A truly researcher-centred FP10 is essential for addressing shared global challenges, securing Europe's strategic autonomy, and maintaining its leadership in science and innovation.

Introduction

As a global community of researchers committed to advancing research excellence and improving the early career researcher's journey, the MCAA actively contributes evidence-based policy feedback to the European Commission, ensuring that EU research and innovation (R&I) programmes empower researchers, foster scientific excellence, and strengthen Europe's competitiveness. Building on [the MCAA's previous policy positions](#), this statement provides a constructive assessment of the ongoing discussions and emerging FP10 and MFF proposals, to ensure FP10 remains a robust, independent, and researcher-centred programme that upholds bottom-up excellence, inclusiveness, and global scientific leadership.

What the MCAA welcomes in the FP10 and MFF proposals

The MCAA welcomes several key aspects of [the proposed FP10 and MFF](#), recognising their potential to strengthen Europe's R&I landscape.

The MCAA strongly welcomes the EC's commitment to retaining Horizon Europe (FP10) as a standalone programme within the next MFF, recognising its crucial role as Europe's flagship R&I funding instrument. The proposed €175 billion budget, representing a significant increase, sends a strong signal of the EU's continued investment in research, talent, and innovation as key drivers of competitiveness and global leadership, underlining that a robust, dedicated R&I programme is essential for Europe's prosperity.

The MCAA applauds the continued and expanded commitment to the European Research Council (ERC) and the MSCA within Pillar 1 'Excellent Science'. These programmes are vital for fostering investigator-driven frontier research, supporting researcher training, career development, and mobility, underpinning Europe's scientific excellence and global attractiveness. The sustained support for these programmes is a testament to their proven impact on generating new knowledge and nurturing top talent.

The MCAA also welcomes the strengthened emphasis within the MSCA on researcher careers, work-life balance, diversity, inclusion, and active support for the European Charter for Researchers. The explicit mention of "support mechanisms to foster sustainable careers" is a crucial step towards addressing systemic issues of career instability and precarity in the research sector and making Europe more attractive to global talent. Furthermore, the MCAA supports simplification measures, as long as these don't compromise the quality and robustness of the review process.

What the MCAA is concerned about in the FP10 and MFF proposals

Despite the positive aspects, the MCAA identifies several key areas of concern that warrant careful attention during the ongoing negotiations to ensure FP10's long-term effectiveness and integrity.

The MCAA shares the widespread concern that the "tight connection" and "single rulebook" with the European Competitiveness Fund (ECF) could compromise FP10's scientific independence and shift its focus from excellence-driven, high quality, bottom-up research, which is needed to address current and future unknown challenges, towards industrial-driven, top-down research that focuses on short-term views within an uncertain geopolitical landscape. This risks undermining the fundamental research that underpins long-term innovation and societal progress, as a purely top-down, industrially-driven approach may overlook the unpredictable discoveries that arise from curiosity-driven research.

Despite simplification goals, the ECF integration and the Competitiveness Coordination Tool (CCT) could increase bureaucratic burden. This could undermine simplified procedures, create friction with industrial policy alignment, and reduce programme agility. While "moonshot" projects offer potential for high-impact breakthroughs and strategic autonomy, the MCAA is concerned about maintaining the balance between these top-down, mission-oriented initiatives and the continued robust support for fundamental, curiosity-driven research across all pillars. Over-emphasis on strategic direction risks stifling the unpredictable discoveries that often lead to unforeseen breakthroughs and limit the breadth of scientific exploration. The new provision allowing the MSCA to target specific thematic priorities or geographical locations "in pursuit of strategic autonomy" is particularly concerning, as it introduces a degree of directionality that could compromise the programme's bottom-up, open-to-all-domains nature. Furthermore,

proposals suggesting that the MSCA may need to contribute to these “moonshot” projects further raise concerns about diluting the programme’s core objectives of researcher training and mobility, or redirecting its budget towards other priorities to the detriment of the sustainability of early career researchers' careers. As stated in the [“No Directionality in MSCA”](#) statement co-signed by the MCAA and 16 other organisations, preserving the MSCA’s bottom-up nature is essential to its proven success in attracting diverse talent and fostering research excellence and sustainable careers.

The proposed FP10 budget of €175 billion, while an increase, remains significantly below the €220 billion recommended by the [Heitor Report](#). This potential gap is particularly concerning for programmes like the MSCA. The [Horizon 2020 evaluation](#) revealed a €159 billion funding gap for high-quality proposals “above the quality thresholds,” highlighting the persistent unmet demand. Considering the urgent need to attract and retain top talent, as stressed in the MCAA’s statement [“Choose Europe: Attracting Global Talent to Build a Stronger ERA,”](#) and to support critical sectors such as AI, quantum, digital, and green technologies essential for Europe’s sustainable growth, the proposed budget is insufficient to meet the EU’s ambitious R&I goals. As outlined in the MCAA’s statement [“Vision for the Next MFF,”](#) a stronger budget commitment is crucial to ensure Europe’s global competitiveness in an increasingly challenging geopolitical context.

The MCAA expresses significant concern regarding the proposed changes to the ERC President selection process. The ERC has been a highly successful and globally renowned programme. These potential changes raise questions about preserving the ERC's scientific independence. Furthermore, the proposed two-year term, extendable only once, would undermine the ERC's long-term strategic planning, weaken the continuity in scientific vision, and potentially expose the ERC to political influence, threatening its status as a globally respected, excellence-driven programme.

Finally, while the MCAA welcomes the reinforcement of international cooperation, the explicit integration of "geo-political considerations, including economic security," marks a significant shift. The MCAA is concerned that a more selective approach to international R&I partnerships, while intended to safeguard EU interests, could inadvertently hinder broader global scientific collaboration on shared challenges and be perceived as protectionist, potentially isolating European researchers from global scientific advancements.

The MCAA's recommendations for a robust and researcher-centric FP10

To ensure FP10 truly empowers Europe's research community and delivers on its ambitious goals, the MCAA puts forward the following recommendations:

Safeguarding FP10's autonomy and excellence

The MCAA strongly advocates for a clear and distinct legal basis and governance for FP10. It is imperative that the established rules, which prioritise scientific excellence and bottom-up approaches, prevail over any new rules introduced by the ECF. The CCT should remain a mechanism for coordination and synergy, not a top-down steering instrument. The MCAA calls for a ringfenced budget for FP10 that truly reflects the ambition for European R&I leadership, ideally exceeding €220 billion as per [expert recommendations](#), to ensure adequate resources for all its pillars and objectives. The MCAA also calls for permanent structures to guarantee the ERC and MSCA's independence, as it has outlined in the joint [ERA Act Wishlist statement](#) with the European Council of Doctoral Candidates and Junior Researchers (Eurodoc).

Sufficient Investment in the MSCA Program and increased budget

The MCAA recommends allocating €25 billion to the MSCA budget under FP10. The rationale behind this figure is grounded in the programme's proven excellence, persistent unmet demand, inflation-adjusted needs, and the growing size of Europe's research workforce. Horizon 2020's evaluation shows a €159 billion shortfall, with 74% of high-quality proposals (~100,000) unfunded, highlighting Europe's failure to capitalise on research. The MSCA alone needed an extra €6 billion for the 2021–2022 proposals, nearly matching its entire €6.6 billion allocation. Over seven years, this unmet demand could reach €21 billion. Combining this with the existing MSCA budget baseline (€6,6 billion) suggests that at least €27,6 billion would be required to adequately support all excellent MSCA proposals. To preserve the real value of funding, inflation must also be considered. Assuming an annual 2% inflation rate over seven years (2024–2031), the purchasing power of €27,6 billion would decline to the equivalent of €31,7 billion in constant euros. The proposed €25 billion allocation is therefore a pragmatic and conservative estimate that acknowledges financial realities while ensuring meaningful support for the research community.

Finally, this investment is necessary to match the scale of Europe's growing research workforce. The number of full-time equivalent (FTE) researchers in Europe has risen by 45% from 1,48 million in 2013 to 2,15 million in 2024. This expanding, increasingly specialised research ecosystem requires a proportional boost in training, mobility, and career development opportunities, which the MSCA is uniquely positioned to deliver. This need for increased investment is also reflected in the historical and projected budget shares of the MSCA within successive framework programmes, as shown in Table 1.

Table 1: Decreasing MSCA budget evolution across the EU Framework Programmes

Programme	Period	Total programme budget (EUR million, current prices)	Pillar I (Excellent Science) budget (EUR million, current prices)	MSCA budget (EUR million, current prices)	MSCA % of Pillar I budget	MSCA % of total programme budget
Horizon 2020	2014–2020	77,028 ¹	24,441 ¹	6,162 ¹	25,21%	8,00%
Horizon Europe	2021–2027	95,500 ²	25,011 ²	6,602 ²	26,40%	6,91%
Horizon Europe (FP10)	2028–2034	175,000	44,100	10,500	23,81%	6,00%

In this context, a €25 billion budget for the MSCA in FP10 is a critical investment for Europe to maintain its scientific leadership, drive innovation, and achieve its ambitious goals of competitiveness, resilience, and strategic autonomy in the global R&I landscape.

Fostering an inclusive European Research Area

The MCAA supports well-resourced widening actions under Pillar IV, including the new "transition countries" category, to effectively reduce R&I disparities across Europe and foster excellence and opportunity across all Member States. Initiatives for talent retention and measures to counteract brain drain are crucial, ensuring that all regions can contribute to and benefit from the ERA, thereby strengthening Europe's overall research capacity.

¹ https://ec.europa.eu/assets/eac/msca/documents/documentation/msca-factsheet_en.pdf

² <https://www.ffg.at/sites/default/files/downloads/HorizonEuropeBudget.pdf>

Strengthening researcher careers and mobility

The MCAA urges a significant increase in the MSCA budget, recognising the substantial unmet demand highlighted above. This increased funding is crucial to support a diverse range of doctoral and postdoctoral researchers across all disciplines and sectors. Boosting the MSCA is also essential to deliver on the ambitions of the Choose Europe initiative, making Europe the destination of choice for top global talent.

Full and effective implementation of the European Charter for Researchers and the Code of Conduct for the Recruitment of Researchers is needed, ensuring fair recruitment, transparent procedures, and attractive working conditions across the European Research Area (ERA). Concrete measures to address researcher precarity, including promoting long-term career prospects and improving work-life balance, are necessary to make Europe the most attractive destination for global talent. At the same time, FP10 should embed research assessment reform across all pillars, aligning with the principles of the Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment (CoARA).

The MSCA must unequivocally remain a bottom-up programme, with its open-to-all-domains nature fully preserved, as reaffirmed in the joint [“No Directionality in MSCA”](#) statement.

Ensuring balanced research priorities

The MCAA calls for continued strong support for fundamental and early-stage collaborative research (low-to-mid Technology Readiness Levels) across all Pillars (see joint statement [“Preserving the foundation of innovation: enhancing early-stage collaborative R&I in FP10”](#) for more). This type of research is irreplaceable for fostering curiosity-driven exploration and breakthrough innovation, forming the bedrock for future societal and industrial advancements. "Moonshot" projects should complement, rather than detract from, the overall funding for

fundamental and collaborative research, with clear mechanisms for integration and impact assessment.

The MCAA advocates for increased and adequate funding for research addressing global societal challenges, particularly within the “Society” cluster of Pillar II, as well as those calls from other clusters where involvement of Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH) is required, ensuring robust support for all disciplines.

Promoting openness and responsible international cooperation

The MCAA advocates for a balanced approach to international cooperation that fosters global and open scientific collaboration on shared challenges while responsibly safeguarding critical technologies and intellectual property. This requires ensuring transparency and proportionality in the application of research security considerations.

The MCAA also calls for FP10 to strengthen support for Open Science as a driver of transparency, collaboration, and global knowledge sharing. It supports the diamond open access model, including platforms like Open Research Europe, and encourages FP10 to provide sustainable funding for such initiatives. Investments in open research infrastructures and incentives for open access to research outputs are essential to ensure that publicly funded research is widely accessible and maximises its academic, economic and societal impact.

Conclusions

The MCAA calls for continued constructive dialogue and collaboration with EU institutions, Member States, and all research stakeholders throughout the negotiation process. The initial reactions from [several stakeholders](#) on the first FP10 proposal underline the need for deeper engagement and alignment to ensure the programme reflects the needs and ambitions of the entire ERA. The MCAA also calls on the EC to [meaningfully consider the insights](#) provided by its advisors and stakeholder communities, such as those outlined in the “Align, Act, Accelerate” report and other stakeholder and expert statements. In this context, sustained and open dialogue is more important than ever. This collective effort is essential to ensure that the final FP10 and MFF truly empower Europe's diverse research community to address global challenges, secure its strategic autonomy, and maintain its leadership in science, technology, and innovation on the global stage

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